

IMMUNO-INFLAMMATORY MARKERS OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION PROGRESSION INTO CORONARY HEART DISEASE

Ganieva Shakhzoda Shavkatovna

Bukhara State Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7793680>

At the world level, research is being conducted aimed at studying the immune mechanisms of the formation of cardiovascular diseases. Consolidation of immuno-inflammatory, genetic and other theories of atherogenesis can be based on deterministic overexpression of cytokine genes affecting production levels, biochemical activity of immune system mediators, expression of adhesion molecules, transformation of monocytes/macrophages and smooth muscle cells into foam cells with subsequent deposition of cholesterol crystals in the intima of blood vessels. It is known that mediators of the immune system – proinflammatory cytokines activate lipid synthesis and affect the redistribution of cholesterol in the cytoplasmic membrane and inside the cell. Therefore, it seems appropriate to analyze the immunogenetic mechanisms of development, progression of atherosclerosis and associated CVD with the participation of mediators of acute and chronic inflammation of the "first wave".

The purpose of the study:

Improvement of diagnostic methods for cardiac remodeling taking into account immuno-inflammatory markers in angina pectoris.

Materials and methods of research: The study included 116 patients, 80 patients hospitalized in the emergency department of the Bukhara branch of the Republican Scientific Center for Emergency Medical Care and patients, 36 patients receiving outpatient treatment in the Bukhara city Family Polyclinic No. 4: The 1st comparison group consists of 36 patients with hypertension (GB) stage 1, coronary heart disease (CHD), stable angina pectoris FC 1; Group 2 consisted of 32 patients with CHD, stable angina pectoris, FC 2, GB 2-stage, 2-degree, risk III; Group 3 consisted of 48 patients with coronary heart disease, stable angina pectoris FC 3, GB 3-stage, grade 3, risk IV. General clinical, biochemical, immunological, functional, anthropometric and statistical research methods were used.

Results: The study of immunological blood parameters in coronary heart disease showed a 3.0-fold increase in IL-1 in patients of the 1st and 2nd groups versus patients of the 3rd group, that is, as angina progresses, there is an increase in the synthesis of proinflammatory cytokine IL-1. The level of IL-6 was found to

increase to 101.0 ± 13.8 pg/ml in stable angina, to 35.8 ± 0.84 pg/ml in unstable angina relative to patients with AH- 15.2 ± 0.86 pg/ml.

During the study of cytokines in selected patients for the study, a decrease in the level of TNF-a in patients with coronary heart disease was revealed to 39.1 ± 1.89 pg/ml compared with the data of patients with hypertension- 50.4 ± 1.74 pg/ml. The study of complement C3 in patients revealed its statistically significant increase in coronary artery disease AS- 58.2 ± 2.07 ng/ml, against hypertensive patients - 53.0 ± 1.15 ng/ml ($p < 0.05$). In patients with coronary heart disease, the concentration of C3 was at the level of group 3 values: 56.2 ± 5.4 ng/ml and 53.0 ± 1.15 ng/ml, respectively. A decrease in the level of TNF-a, characteristic of the progression of hypertension in CHD, was revealed in patients with CHD SSN to 39.1 ± 1.89 pg/ml compared with the indicators of patients with hypertension- 50.4 ± 1.74 pg/ml, which was not typical for atypical angina. This leads to the conclusion that in hypertension, as a result of inflammation of blood vessels and microcirculation disorders at the tissue level, the breakdown of myocyte cells occurs. As hypertension progresses in CHD, apoptosis and cell death occur at the tissue level, in response to which the compensatory mechanisms of the body's defense are activated. In confirmation of this conclusion, the study found a statistically significant increase in complement C3 in the atypical form of angina pectoris (58.2 ± 2.07 ng/ml), against hypertensive patients - 53.0 ± 1.15 ng/ml ($p < 0.05$). And in patients with stable angina pectoris, the concentration of C3 was at the level of group 3 values: 56.2 ± 5.4 ng/ml and 53.0 ± 1.15 ng/ml, respectively.

Conclusion. Consequently, the results of the study show the importance of taking into account syntropy in the relationship of the mechanism of progression of hypertension in coronary heart disease with immuno-biochemical factors of growth and damage. Depending on the state of the syntropy, as the period of hypertension progresses, it progresses into coronary artery disease with subsequent multiple organ failure. Thus, the mechanism of hypertension progression in CHD is closely interrelated with vascular endothelial dysfunction. The activity of growth factors and inflammatory markers is of important prognostic value for assessing the progression of CVD and the development of other complications.